

A STUDY ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN THE CURRICULUM OF INDIAN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

India is one among the fastest growing economies in the world. The modern era has brought many opportunities to bring changes in multiple fields. Introduction of globalisation, industrialisation and commercialisation brought an immense transformation in various aspects of life. Entrepreneurship play a key role in the economic development of a country. The major problems like unemployment and poverty are addressed by entrepreneurship. Various support initiatives like Make in India, Start Up -Stand Up India, Skill India are taken by Government of India after considering all the benefits to the society as a whole. Competency factors like innovation and creativity came into limelight with the advent of industrialisation and advancement of technology in the all field. The entrepreneurs are considered as ‘change agents’ in the process of economic development of a nation. Entrepreneurship development now-a-days require entrepreneurial education. Imparting entrepreneurship education to students at their higher education level enable them to develop the required potential and skills. Entrepreneurial education considered to be an important and influential force shaping the wellbeing of an economy. Effective entrepreneurial education fosters positive entrepreneurial attitude and motivate students to start their own venture. Entrepreneurship education includes all activities aiming to foster entrepreneurial mindsets, attitude and skills and covering wide range of aspects such as idea generation, start up, growth and innovation. Despite several entrepreneurship programmes are developed by Government and higher education institutions to support the entrepreneurship movement very little is known about effectiveness of entrepreneurship programme implementation. The purpose of this study is to verify the effectiveness of implementation of entrepreneurship programme in higher education curriculum, thereby providing training to students to cultivate and improvise their skill to grow into be a successful entrepreneur.

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Key words: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneur, Curriculum, Skill, Government initiatives, Education.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new and assuming the risks and rewards. It is the individual's ability to translate idea into actions. Entrepreneurs are considered as 'change agents' in the process of economic development of a nation. The major problems like unemployment and poverty are addressed by entrepreneurship. Make in India, Start Up -Stand Up India, Skill India are taken by Government. Entrepreneurship development now-a-days require entrepreneurial education. Entrepreneurship education at the university level is important to build generations of leaders for global innovation. The role of education in producing entrepreneurs is enormous. The entrepreneurship creation process through education depends upon the quality of education and presence of environment encouraging innovation. Imparting entrepreneurship education to students at their higher education level enable them to develop the required potential and skills. Entrepreneurship education is becoming a major force in all over the world. Entrepreneurship education has been formally recognised in universities since 1940 by US. Countries like US, European Union, Japan, China, etc. have been taken a leading role in promoting entrepreneurship education. Today educational institutions are producing lakhs of students in different sectors. In the competitive world it has become obstacle for students to choose the right career. Therefore, this study focuses to know the entrepreneurship interest among students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the importance of entrepreneurship education in India
- To understand the opinion of students on introducing entrepreneurial development training at their higher education level
- To suggest effective measures to improve the quality of entrepreneurship education in India

SIGNIFICANCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN INDIA

According to 2011 Census the youth population (age-group 15-24) in India account for one-fifth (i.e., 19.1%) of total population and it is expected to 34.33% by 2020. The University education system has vital responsibility in directing this massive young population for betterment of their life as well as betterment of society as a whole. To enhance economic growth of India it has to give

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employment opportunity and social welfare to its young people and it can be provided by entrepreneur. Universities all over India cantered in upbringing the wage-earning professionals which results in unemployment where qualified students having less viable knowledge.

KIND OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROGRAMMES SHOULD BE INCLUDED

Entrepreneurship orientation and awareness programme which focus on general information about entrepreneurship and encourage participants to think in terms of entrepreneurship as a career. Skill development training sessions and workshops should be conducted by inviting entrepreneurs in various fields. Training should focus on entrepreneurial behaviour, attributes and skills. New enterprise creation programmes designed to develop competencies that lead to self-employment, economic self-sufficiency or employment generation. Even after UGC guidelines on introducing entrepreneurship as a curriculum at UG level still it is not properly implemented. Despite several entrepreneurship programmes are developed by Government very low or no efforts taken by Higher education institutions in this regard. Only the theoretical knowledge about the subject is given to students and no extra efforts taken to expose them to reality.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study undertaken considers both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected by a field survey using questionnaire and interview method. A sample of 60 in Mangaluru Taluk was selected on random basis. Structured questionnaires were distributed among these respondents and the data was collected and processed using statistical tools. The secondary data was obtained from various journals, blogs and websites.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1: STUDENTS INTEREST TO START NEW BUSINESS

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Interested	42	70
Not interested	18	30
Total	60	100

Table 1 portrays that out of 60 student 42 students are interested to start their own business after studies and 18 students are not interested in stating business of their own. Majority of

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respondents have shown interest towards business start-ups

TABLE 2: ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT CELL IN INSTITUTIONS

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Have	0	00
Do not have	60	100
Total	60	100

Table 2 depicts that out of 60 respondents in total, norespondents are having Entrepreneurship Development cells in their Institution.

Table 3: PARTIPATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Participated	39	65
Not participated	21	35
Total	60	100

Table 3 shows that out of 60 students in total 39 students, that is 65% attended this kind of programme, rest 21 students (i.e., 35 %) have not attend such programmes.

Table 4: PREFERENCE TO FOCUS PRESENT SYSTEM EDUCATION ONENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Required	52	87
Not required	8	13
Total	60	100

Table 4 shows that out of total respondents 52students said that present education system should focus on entrepreneurship development and remaining 8 respondents not shown any interest towards the same.

Table 5: ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION DEVELOPS CREATIVITY AND SELF CONFIDENCE

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	33	55

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Agree	27	45
Neutral	0	00
Disagree	0	00
Strongly disagree	0	00
Total	60	100

Table 5 depicts that out of 60 students in total, 33 respondents that is 55% are strongly agreed that entrepreneurship development programme develop their creative thinking and self-confidence and 27 respondents (accounts for 45%) are agreed with this.

Table 6: ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS SUBJECT CAN HELP YOUTHS IN THEIR NEW BUSINESS

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	18
Agree	49	82
Neutral	0	00
Disagree	0	00
Strongly disagree	0	00
Total	60	100

Table 6 shows that out of total respondents, 11 respondents, that is 18% are strongly agree with the statement that imparting entrepreneurship as a subject at higher education level may help them in future when they take up new venture and remaining 49 respondents also agree with the same.

Table 7: ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION IS MANDATORY

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	58	97
Agree	2	3
Total	60	100

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Table 7 shows that out of total 60, 58 students said it is better if entrepreneurial education made mandatory in all educational institutions.

FINDINGS

- It can be noticed that, most of the students are interested in business start-ups.
- The result of the study finds that, most of the institutions in Mangalore do not have entrepreneurship development cells.
- Majority of respondents strongly agree that, entrepreneurship education develops creativity and self confidence in students and attending entrepreneurship development programme develops their technical skill as well.
- Study tells that, if entrepreneurial education is made mandatory in all educational institution then it will be helpful tool for students who wants to build their career as an entrepreneur.

SUGGESTIONS

- The educational institutes should focus more on creativity and innovation of students while designing the curriculum activity.
- Motivation and awareness of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education should be provided to all students
- Entrepreneurship development cells should be formed in all Educational Institutions
- Entrepreneurship education and training should not be limited to the specific institutions rather it should be provided by almost every educational institute
- They should arrange programme related to entrepreneurship.
- Business events must be organized to enhance the creativity, innovativeness of the youths, to increase the social interaction, communication skills and develop the personality of the students.

CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship is one of the best solutions for unemployment problem in the country.

But it is not easy to effectively play the role of an entrepreneur and the only way to convert a person into an effective entrepreneur is by equipping them all the necessary skills.

Entrepreneurship education plays an important role in entrepreneurial skill development. The

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role of educational institutions in entrepreneurship development cannot be neglected as these are the breeding pools for the entrepreneurs. In India the awareness about the entrepreneurship is still low due to various factors. Individuals still prefer to seek for employment rather than starting their own venture. This is because our education system is designed such that it kills creativity and innovation and does not concentrate on development of entrepreneurship.

There is a need for educational institutions to realize their importance and role in entrepreneurship development and should facilitate the students to develop multi-disciplinary skills and find innovative solutions to the problems faced by the people in the society. Also, the government should take some measures regarding promotion and development of entrepreneurial education. And several measures should be taken both by the government and educational institutions to support and promote entrepreneurial education.

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